
Patent Application

System to Rescue Person - Blue Blocks Complete School

APPLICANT

Blue Blocks Complete School

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DOCUMENTS INCLUDED

Abstract

Drawings (Fig. 1, Fig. 2)

Provisional Specification (Form 2)

Declaration as to Inventorship (Form 5)

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SYSTEM TO RESCUE PERSON

ABSTRACT

A system to rescue a person from a borehole. The system comprises a controller configured to receive inputs from a rescuer and a rescue unit communicatively coupled to the controller for receiving control signals provided by the rescuer. The rescue unit comprises retractable wings configured to retract and expand based on a size of the borehole, at least one sensor to provide data to the rescue unit to enable the retractable wings to retract and expand, at least one camera to capture images along the borehole to enable the rescuer to manage a flight of the rescue unit along the borehole, and a foldable platform to carry the person from the borehole.

FIG. 1

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FIG. 2

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FORM 2

THE PATENTS ACT, 1970

(39 of 1970)

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THE PATENTS RULES, 2003

PROVISIONAL SPECIFICATION

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1. TITLE OF THE INVENTION

SYSTEM TO RESCUE PERSON

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2. APPLICANT(S)

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3. PREAMBLE TO DESCRIPTION

20 **PROVISIONAL SPECIFICATION**

The following specification describes the invention

FIELD OF THE INVENTION

The present invention relates generally to rescue purposes, and more specifically, to a system to rescue a person from a borehole.

BACKGROUND

5 Boreholes (such a borewells, manholes) are often created for a variety of purposes such as water and mineral extraction, soil testing, repair work and the like. However, many such borewells are left unfilled or uncovered. As a result, there have been many cases of individuals falling into such borewells. Typically, such borewells are often deep and if any individual falls into such borewell it can be life
10 threatening event if the individual is not rescued quickly.

Generally, to enable rescue of such individual, a rope may be used to pull out such individual from the borehole. However, it is will be difficult for any individual to hold the rope and come out of the borehole due to space constrain and inappropriate terrain inside the borehole. Sometimes, another individual is sent inside the
15 borehole to rescue the individual from the borehole. However, it is difficult for another individual to go inside the borehole due to the space constrain and this may cause stones and/or soil around or along the borehole to fall on the individual inside the borehole. Alternatively, to rescue such individuals, another borehole (which may be bigger in shape) may be made adjacent to the borehole in which the
20 individual is struck and thereafter the boreholes may be connected to rescue the individual using the new and wide borehole. However, such a technique of rescuing a person is often time consuming, resource intensive and in certain extreme situations ineffective.

Therefore, in light of the foregoing discussion, there exists a need to overcome the
25 aforementioned drawbacks of conventional rescue systems and techniques.

OBJECT OF THE INVENTION

The object of the present disclosure is to provide a system to rescue a person from a borehole. Typically, object of the present disclosure is to provide quick and

efficient way of helping to rescue the person from the borehole. The help can be provided in a strategic manner based on the situation in hand. Typically, the system employs a rescue unit, which is communicably coupled to the controller to receive control signals provided by a rescuer. The rescue unit is equipped with sensors to assess and/or analyze the situation, which enables in strategically carrying out the rescue operation. The rescue unit includes retractable wings and sensors that enables the rescues unit to move along the borehole, and a foldable platform for carrying the person from the borehole.

SUMMARY OF THE INVENTION

In one aspect, the present disclosure provides a system to rescue a person from a borehole. The system comprises a controller configured to receive inputs from a rescuer and a rescue unit communicatively coupled to the controller for receiving control signals provided by the rescuer. The rescue unit comprises retractable wings configured to retract and expand based on a size of the borehole, at least one sensor to provide data to the rescue unit to enable the retractable wings to retract and expand, at least one camera to capture images along the borehole to enable the rescuer to manage a flight of the rescue unit along the borehole, and a foldable platform to carry the person from the borehole.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DRAWINGS

The present disclosure will now be described, by way of example only, with reference to the following diagrams wherein:

Figure 1 is a block diagram of a system to rescue a person from a borehole, in accordance with an emodiment of the present disclosure, and

Figure 2 is a top view of exemplary retractable wings of a rescue unit of the system of FIG. 1, in accordance with an emodiment of the present disclosure.

DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF ILLUSTRATIVE EMBODIMENTS

The embodiments of the present dislcosure can be best understood with Figure 1, depicting a block diagram of a system **100** to rescue a person from a borehole. The

system **100** comprises a controller **102** configured to receive inputs from a rescuer (not shown) and a rescue unit **104** communicably coupled to the controller **102** to receive the control signals provided by the rescuer.

5 The rescue unit **104** includes retractable wings (shown in Figure 2) configured to retract and expand based on a size of the borehole. The rescue unit **104** also includes at least one sensor to provide data to the rescue unit **104** to enable the retractable wings to retract and expand. The rescue unit **104** further includes at least one camera to capture images along the borehole to enable the rescuer to manage a flight of the rescue unit **104** along the borehole. Further, the rescue unit **104** includes a foldable
10 platform to carry the person from the borehole.

In an embodiment, the controller **102** may be a control device operable to communicate control signals from the rescuer to the rescue unit **104**. The control signal may be a pulse or frequency of electricity or light that carries data for a control command as it travels over a network, a computer channel or wireless.
15 Further, the controller **102** may be a computing device having elements, such as a display, control buttons or joysticks, processor, memory and the like. For example, the controller **102** is a portable computing device having one or more buttons operable to be pressed to generate the control signal. Notably, the controller **102** comprises at least one of a hardware button or a virtual button. Further, the
20 controller **102** is operable to control movements of the rescue unit **104** employing one or more embedded and/or external devices such as a GPS, microphone, one or more sensors. The one or more buttons of the controller **102** is pressed by a rescuer to generate the control signals. Further, the control signal may be associated with the observed information of the rescue unit **104** employing one or more sensors.
25 The said one or more sensors are selected from the group of sensors including, but not limited to light sensors, accelerometers, gyroscope sensors, proximity sensor, temperature sensor, pressure sensor, smoke sensors and so forth.

In an embodiment, the rescue unit **104** may be an unmanned aerial vehicle, such as a drone, a quadcopter. Further, the rescue unit **104** may be multi rotor drone, fixed
30 wing drone, single rotor helicopter, and the like. Further, variety of sized drones

based upon the requirement may be used such as, but not limited to, micro UAV's or MAV's. However, it is to be understood that the wings of the rescue unit **104** have to be retractable in nature.

Typically, the rescue unit **104** is managed by a computer program and/or electronic circuitry. The rescue unit **104** is capable of performing three-dimensional movements for rescuing the person. Notably, the rescue unit **104** is enabled with an image capturing device, microphone and a speaker for collecting and/or transmitting audio-visual information pertinent to the person and/or the borehole. Further, the rescue unit **104** comprises of at least one sensor from a group of sensors including, but not limited to, a gyroscope, MEMS (Micro-Electromechanical Systems), accelerometer, acoustic sensors, light sensors, pressure sensor, smoke sensor, heat sensor, proximity sensor and the like. The rescue unit **104** includes at least one processor. The processor includes, but is not limited to, a microprocessor, a microcontroller, a complex instruction set computing or any other type of processing circuit. Additionally, the at least one processor, processing devices and elements are arranged in various architectures for responding to and processing the instructions that drive the rescue unit **104**.

The rescue unit **104** employs one or more methods such as, but not limited to, image capturing, thermal imaging, infrared imaging, audio-visual detection, proximity sensing and the like, while rescuing the person. Beneficially, the at least one camera and/or at least one sensor is used for determining the size and terrain of the borehole. The at least one camera employing one or more lenses either separately or in combination to exploit its optical characteristics. The optical characteristics are used to compare a known measure against an object such as the underground structure or borehole to determine dimensional information including height, width, curvature of the borehole and with operational details for the rescue. The operational details including internal state of underground structure such as gases present in the borehole, maximum permissible point of contact with the person in case of space shortage, final or desired location of the rescue unit **104** in or near the underground structure. Optionally, the rescue unit **104** may include a sound

transmitter and a sound receiver to enable communication of the rescuer with the person in the borehole.

In an embodiment, the at least one sensor is an anti-collision sensor that provides the data to the rescue unit **104** to enable protection from collisions with walls of the borehole by retracting or expanding the retractable wings based on the senses data.

In another embodiment, the system **100** may include a gas detecting sensor to detect presence of any poisonous gas in the borehole. Based on detection of presence of the poisonous gas, safety measure may be taken, for example, providing oxygen supply into the borehole, providing mask and the like.

In another embodiment, the rescue unit **104** comprises a light emitting device to enable noiseless capturing of the images. The term 'noiseless capturing' refers to the undisturbed transmission of visual information. Further, said visual information is transmitted in real time or in a near real time scenario for efficient controlling of the rescue unit **104** by the rescuer.

The rescue unit **104** is configured to determine a course of action based on control inputs from a rescuer provided through the controller **102**. The course of action is determined by the rescuer from visual analysis of the borehole. In case the rescuer is unable to provide a controlling input to the rescue unit **104**, the rescue unit **104** is configured to determine the course of action based on physical properties of the borehole, situation of the person. The physical properties of the borehole may include information such as diameter, depth, curvature or bends of the borehole. Further, the situation of the person may be judged based on the audio and visual data collected for the person. Additionally, the sensed or observed information may include sensor information from the at least one sensor such as gas or smoke detector, temperature sensor and the like. Moreover, the rescue unit **104** is operable to assess or analyze the situation (to determine the course of action) based on capturing the audio-visual information and processing the said information through pre-trained machine learning models. The rescue unit **104** may be also used for providing essential things, like water to avoid dehydration of user, medicine in case

of an unforeseen situation and so forth, and this may be done using a customized robotic arm of the rescue unit **104**.

The rescue unit **104** unit communicatively coupled to the controller **102**, to receive control signals provided by the rescuer. The communication coupling may be a
5 wireless communication, a wired communication or any combination thereof. For example, a communication network may be used as communication means between the rescue unit **104** and the controller **102**. Further, the communication network may include but is not limited to Local Area Networks (LANs), Wide Area Networks (WANs), Metropolitan Area Networks (MANs), Wireless LANs (WLANs),
10 Wireless WANs (WWANs), Wireless MANs (WMANs), the Internet, second generation (2G) telecommunication networks, third generation (3G) telecommunication networks, fourth generation (4G) telecommunication networks, fifth generation (5G) telecommunication networks and Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX) networks.

15 In an example, the rescue unit **104** is configured to receive a signal from the controller **102** to initiate a movement. Thereafter, the rescue unit **104** upon receiving signals from the controller **102** is configured to provide visual and sensed information to the controller **102** using at least one sensor and at least one camera on a real-time basis for controlling inputs provided by the rescuer. Notably, the
20 rescue unit **104** receives control inputs in the form of control signals from the controller **102** to control movement inside the borehole. The rescue unit **104** may further receive a signal from the controller **102** upon reaching a desired location in the borehole. Notably, the said signal is a control signal for employing the foldable platform to receive the person on the platform. Finally, the rescue unit **104** may be
25 provided with a signal to move along the borehole to carry the person from the borehole.

Figure 2 is a top view of the exemplary retractable wings 200 of the rescue unit **104**. In operation, the retractable wings are configured to or expand or retract based on a size of the borehole, which is determined by employing the audio-visual
30 information. The retractable wings edges are configured to be shaped in a manner

to accommodate the size of the hole in an efficient manner. According to an embodiment, the retractable wings employ a scissor hinge mechanism.

While the disclosed subject matter has been described in conjunction with a number of embodiments, it is evident that many alternatives, modifications and variations would be or are apparent to those of ordinary skill in the applicable arts. Accordingly, applicant intends to embrace all such alternatives, modifications, equivalents, and variations that are within the spirit and scope of the disclosed subject matter described herein.

We Claim:

1. A system to rescue a person from a borehole, the system comprises:
- a controller configured to receive inputs from a rescuer; and
- a rescue unit communicatively coupled to the controller for receiving control signals provided by the rescuer, the rescue unit comprises:

- 5 - retractable wings configured to retract and expand based on a size of the borehole;
 - at least one sensor to provide data to the rescue unit to enable the retractable wings to retract and expand;
 - at least one camera to capture images along the borehole to enable the rescuer to manage a flight of the rescue unit along the borehole; and
10 - a foldable platform to carry the person from the borehole.

2. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein the at least one sensor is an anti-collision sensor that provides the data to the rescue unit to enable protection from collisions with walls of the borehole by retracting or expanding the retractable wings.
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3. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein the system further comprises a gas detecting sensor to detect presence of any poisonous gas in the borehole.

20 4. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein the rescue unit further comprises a light emitting device to enable noiseless capturing of the images.

5. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein the rescue unit further comprises a sound transmitter and a sound receiver to enable communication of the rescuer with the person in the borehole.
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Agent for the Applicant

FORM 5
THE PATENTS ACT, 1970
(39 of 1970)
&
The Patents Rules, 2003
DECLARATION AS TO INVENTORSHIP
[See section 10(6) and rule 13(6)]

1. NAME OF APPLICANT(S):

We **Blue Blocks complete school** an **India** organization of **Blue Blocks complete school**, **Mig 3, APHB colony, Gachibowli 500032, Hyderabad, Telangana, India**, hereby authorize,

that the true and first inventor(s) of the invention disclosed in the Provisional/complete specification filed in pursuance of my/our application numbered Dated **25 June 2020** is/are.

2. INVENTOR(S)

Name	Nationality	Address
Dhairya singh bangari	India	[REDACTED]
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Ayushmaan	India	[REDACTED]

Dated this 25 day of June 2020

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Sarasija Padmanabhan

[REDACTED]

Agent for the applicant

To

The Controller of Patents

The Patent Office, At Chennai